

Effects of Different Heat Treatment Conditions on Microstructure and Hardness of AISI 1040 and 5140 Steels

Salih Bilal Çetinkal¹, Gökhan Arıcı^{1*}

¹Department of Metallurgical and Materials Engineering, Faculty of Technology, Selcuk University, Türkiye

*(arici@selcuk.edu.tr)

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Abstract –In this study, the microstructure and hardness behavior of AISI 1040 and AISI 5140 steel samples were investigated after heat treatment with austenitizing for different durations and cooling in different environments. In the study, samples were austenitized at 850°C for 1 and 5 hours, and then cooled in air, water, and ice water. Microstructure and hardness analyses were performed on the samples after heat treatment. Ferrite and pearlite phases were observed in air-cooled samples, while martensite phases were observed in water and ice water-cooled samples. The hardness of air-cooled samples was lower than that of water-cooled samples, and also lower than that of ice water-cooled samples. Cracks formed in water and ice water-cooled samples. The Cr element in the composition of AISI 5410 steel increases hardenability and increases the martensite ratio formed. This directly contributes to the increase in hardness. Consequently, it has been shown that achieving maximum hardness is not always desirable in terms of mechanical properties, and that optimum values should be determined, taking into account the risk of cracking.

Keywords – AISI 1040, AISI 5140, Microstructure, Hardness, Microcrack.

I. INTRODUCTION

Iron (Fe), one of the most common elements in the world, is the basic component of steel materials. Steel is essentially a type of alloy enriched with carbon dissolved in an Fe matrix. Steel materials are used in many engineering applications due to the wide range of options they offer in terms of mechanical strength, formability, heat treatment capability, and cost. Steels vary among themselves according to their carbon content and alloy types. Carbon steels and alloy steels form the two main groups of this broad family of materials. The carbon content in the steel structure or the presence of alloying elements directly affects the performance of the steel under service conditions. Thanks to the effects of alloying elements, their areas of application are expanding.

AISI 1040 steel, which has a carbon content of approximately 0.40%, is one of the basic steel materials that is low-cost and widely used due to its simple chemical composition [1, 2]. In contrast, AISI 5140 steel, which has the same carbon content, additionally contains 0.8–1.1% chromium (Cr). Thanks to its alloying element, it exhibits superior performance compared to AISI 1040 steel in terms of properties such as hardness, wear resistance, and fatigue strength [3-5].

AISI 1040 steel is widely used in the machine and manufacturing industries. It is used in various machine parts, automotive parts, molds, fixtures, and many other areas [6]. AISI 5140 steels are generally used in tools such as bearings, gears, shafts, gearboxes, axles, pipe and rod applications, screwdrivers, and drill bits that require high strength and hardness, due to their suitability for hot working and moderate weldability [7]. Due to their high strength and toughness properties, they are used in the automotive, agricultural, and construction sectors [8]. Studies have been conducted on the optimum machining performance of AISI 1040 and AISI 5140 steels, particularly in recent years, due to technological developments in the field of machining [9, 10]. In addition to machining performance, the development of the industry has led to an increase in studies on the working performance of materials. Heat treatment processes applied to change the mechanical, physical, and microstructural properties of steels in the desired direction are also coming to the fore. Heat treatment is preferred to obtain properties that cannot be achieved with chemical composition through microstructure control. AISI 1040 and AISI 5140 steels are commonly subjected to heat treatments (austenitizing, quenching, tempering, etc.) due to their classification as medium-carbon steels. Depending on the type of heat treatment, the steel's properties such as hardness, strength, ductility, toughness, and wear resistance can be significantly altered.

Within the scope of this study, AISI 1040 and AISI 5140 steels with the same carbon content were subjected to quenching processes under different cooling parameters (air, water, iced water). The resulting changes in hardness and microstructure of the material were examined.

II. MATERIALS AND METHOD

In the study, 15 mm diameter shafts made of AISI 1040 and AISI 5140 steel materials, whose chemical compositions are given in Table 1, were used. For all heat treatments to be performed, 7 pieces 15 mm long were cut from the shafts. The cut pieces and the processes to be performed are given in Table 2.

Table 1. Chemical composition of AISI 1040 and AISI 5140 steels (wt. %)

	C	Mn	Cr	Si	Fe
AISI 1040	0,44	0,65	0,09	0,20	Bal.
AISI 5140	0,43	0,71	0,92	0,23	Bal.

Table 2. Quenching conditions for AISI 1040 and AISI 5140 samples and austenitizing durations

	Air cooling		Water cooling		Iced water cooling	
AISI 1040	1 h	5 h	1 h	5 h	1 h	5 h
AISI 5140						

The samples were heat treated in a Protherm brand furnace model furnace. First, 850°C was selected as the appropriate austenitizing temperature for all materials. After the furnace temperature was heated to 750°C, the samples were placed inside the furnace. One hour after the furnace temperature reached 850°C, the first group was removed from the furnace and cooled sequentially in air, water, and ice water. The remaining samples in the furnace were left at 850°C for 5 hours, then removed from the furnace and cooled in air, water, and ice water, respectively. The temperature-time variation of the heat treatment performed is detailed in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of heat treatment process

Standard metallography techniques were used for microstructure analysis. First, grinding was performed sequentially from 180 to 2000 grit using SiC sandpaper on a Metkon brand grinding machine. After grinding, the samples were polished by applying a 3 μm diamond solution onto a broadcloth. To obtain a better image, all samples were polished again by applying 1 μm diamond solution onto broadcloth. After the polishing process was completed, a 5% nital solution was prepared and etching was performed to reveal the microstructures. Etching was performed for different durations for AISI 1040 and AISI 5140 steels.

Hardness measurements were taken from all reference samples cut from AISI 1040 and AISI 5140 steel shafts and heat-treated samples. The hardness test was performed using the Vickers method on a Bulut Makine hardness tester at the HV100 setting (100 kg indentation force).

III. RESULTS

Figures 2a and b show the microstructure images obtained after 1 hour and 5 hours of austenitizing and air quenching of the AISI 1040 sample. Figures 2c and d show the microstructure images obtained after 1 hour and 5 hours of austenitizing and air quenching of the AISI 5140 sample. When examining Figure 2a, pearlite and ferrite phases are observed in the samples after 1 hour of austenitizing. Similarly, ferrite and pearlite phases are seen in Figure 2a. It is observed that the grain size increases significantly after 5 hours of austenitization. When examining AISI 5140 steel, it is seen that ferrite and pearlite structures are present after 1 hour of austenitization, but the grains are much finer than those in 1040 steel under the same conditions. A similar situation is seen at 5 hours, and the grain sizes are much finer than those in the 1040 sample austenitized under the same conditions. Ferrite and pearlite are again observed in the structure. Under these conditions, no martensite phase is observed in the steels.

Fig. 2. Microstructures of AISI 1040 and AISI 5140 samples obtained after 1 hour and 5 hours of austenitizing and air cooling
a) 1040-1h, b)1040-5h, c) 5140-1h d) 5140-5h

Figures 3a and 3b show the microstructure images of the AISI 1040 sample after 1 and 5 hours of austenitizing and water quenching. Figures 2c and 2d show the microstructures of AISI 5140 steel after 1 and 5 hours of austenitizing followed by water quenching. The needle-like martensite phase is clearly visible in all samples. It can be noted that the martensite plates become coarser, especially in the 1040 sample, depending on the length of the austenitizing time.

Fig. 3. Microstructures of AISI 1040 and AISI 5140 samples obtained after 1 hour and 5 hours of austenitizing and water cooling a) 1040-1h, b)1040-5h, c) 5140-1h d) 5140-5h

Figures 4a and 4b show the microstructure images of the AISI 1040 sample after 1 and 5 hours of austenitizing followed by ice water quenching. Figures 3c and 3d show the microstructures of AISI 5140 steel after 1 and 5 hours of austenitizing followed by ice water quenching. A needle-like martensite phase is observed in all samples. Under these conditions, similar to ice water quenching, it is possible to encounter thicker martensite plates after 5 hours of austenitizing.

Fig. 4. Microstructures of AISI 1040 and AISI 5140 samples obtained after 1 hour and 5 hours of austenitizing and iced water cooling a) 1040-1h, b)1040-5h, c) 5140-1h d) 5140-5h

Figure 5 shows the hardness values measured after cooling in air, water, and ice water for samples austenitized at 850°C for 1 hour, and Figure 6 shows the hardness values measured after cooling in air, water, and ice water for samples austenitized at 5 hours.

Fig. 5. Fig. Hardnesses of the samples after 1 hour annealing and cooling

It is clearly observed that hardness increases for both samples with increasing cooling rate. Furthermore, a similar trend was observed in hardness across all samples with increasing austenitizing time, and it was determined that hardness decreased. When comparing sample types, it was found that the hardness of the plain carbon sample (AISI 1040) was higher than that of the low-alloy sample (AISI 5140) compared to the unalloyed sample (AISI 1040) with the given compositions in Table 1, indicating that the alloying elements increased the hardness and that hardness was measured higher in all environments. Among all samples and heat treatment parameters, the highest hardness value was observed in the AISI 5140 sample cooled in ice water at 709 HV, while the lowest hardness was measured in the AISI 1040 sample at 205 HV. The hardness obtained after quenching is consistent with martensite hardness. The hardness obtained after air quenching shows the hardness of ferrite and pearlite structures.

Fig. 6. Hardnesses of the samples after 5 hour annealing and cooling

IV. DISCUSSION

Examination of the obtained microstructures clearly shows that the austenitizing time directly affects grain size. With increasing time, grain growth occurred through the diffusion mechanism. However, due to the high Cr content in 5140 steel, the grains in the microstructure appear to be finer. Cr is a carbide-forming element and suppresses grain coarsening [11, 12]. Furthermore, the suppression of ferrite by Cr [13] is clearly seen in Figure 2c.

Cracks are observed in all samples after quenching in water. Rapid cooling caused cracking in the samples due to the brittle martensite phase's tendency to crack [14]. The Cr phase shifts the TTT nose to the right, triggering the formation of finer martensite [12, 15]. Simultaneously, the volume increase in the martensite phase causes stress and consequently crack formation in the samples. In 1040 steel, the martensite exhibits a coarser and somewhat more heterogeneous structure.

Similar interpretations can be made regarding the effect of the Cr element for iced water cooled samples. Under these conditions, cracking occurred in all samples, which is due to the excessive stress experienced in the parts at the high cooling rate.

When hardness is examined according to material type, the fact that the hardness of the AISI 1040 sample, which is an unalloyed plain carbon steel, is lower after quenching compared to AISI 5140 steel is directly related to the Cr content in AISI 5140 steel [16]. Cr contributes to increased hardness by

dissolving in the iron lattice and forming a solid solution, and also increases the hardenability of the steel [15]. Cr shifts the critical nose to the right in continuous cooling curves [17]. This extends the time required for martensite formation, meaning that martensite can be obtained even under slower cooling conditions. In other words, Cr in alloyed steel forms harder and finer martensite due to these effects, directly contributing to the increase in hardness. In addition, the chromium element has carbide-forming properties, and its addition in high proportions ensures the presence of carbides in the microstructure and further increases hardness. The effect of Cr is also clearly seen after air quenching. Cr increases hardness by slowing down ferrite formation and creating carbide [18], thereby forming a finer microstructure. When considering the effect of austenitizing time, increasing the time causes the austenite grains to coarsen (Figure 2), and consequently, the presence of a coarser grain structure after quenching directly leads to a decrease in hardness.

As the quenching intensity increased, the hardness levels also increased, and due to the excessive stress on the samples, cracks occurred in both water and ice water quenching. This clearly shows that hardness increase alone should not be considered as a criterion in the samples.

V. CONCLUSION

The findings from the analysis of heat-treated AISI 1040 and 5140 steel samples are as follows:

- The hardness of AISI 1040 samples is higher than that of AISI 5140 samples when subjected to heat treatments under the same conditions.
- Ferrite and perlite were observed in the microstructure of samples after quenching in air, while martensite was observed in the microstructure after quenching in water and ices water cooling.
- As the cooling rate increases, the hardness of the samples increases.
- Cracking occurs in the samples after cooling in water and iced water cooling.

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